

ANTHRACNOSE DISEASE OF GRAPEVINE

Khodjamkulova Sitora Sulaymanovna

Doctoral candidate at the Research Institute for
Plant Quarantine and Protection

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14499150>

Annotatsiya. Bu maqolada tokda uchraydigan antraknoz kasalligining Surxondaryo viloyati tumanlar bo'yicha tarqalishi va rivojlanishi, zarari, o'simlikdagi kasallik belgilari haqida aytib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar. antraknoz, nav, kasallik, rivojlanish, tarqalish, namlik, harorat

Аннотация. Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются распространение и развитие антракноза винограда в районах Сурхандарьинской области, его вредоносное воздействие, а также симптомы заболевания на растении.

Ключевые слова. антракноз, сорт, болезнь, развитие, распространение, влажность, температура

Annotation. Abstract. This article discusses the distribution and progression of anthracnose disease in grapevines across the districts of Surkhandarya Region, its detrimental effects, and the symptoms of the disease observed in the plant.

Key words. anthracnose, variety, disease, development, distribution, humidity, temperature

In recent years, the annual increase in the world's population has led to an increase in demand for food, including grape products. The grape (*Vitis vinifera* L.) plant is one of the main fruits and food products in the world and is currently grown in more than 100 countries. The volume of the global grape market is estimated at \$215.17 billion in 2024 and is expected to reach \$303.20 billion by 2029, increasing by 7.10% at the CAGR level during the forecast period (2024-2029). According to FAO, grapes produce over 100 million tons of harvest per year and are an important primary source of energy for human nutrition. The increasing prevalence of anthracnose, one of the fungal diseases of vineyards, attracts the attention of phytopathologists and plant protection specialists in many countries. In this regard, the use of advanced resource-saving methods of disease control, taking into account their spread and development, is crucial for preventing disease damage.

№	Farms	Varieties	Disease prevalence, in %.	Disease progression, %.	Average shoot length, cm.		Lagging in the growth of sick plant shoots compared to healthy ones, %.
					Healthy	Diseased	
Oltinsoy District							
1	Soxibkor farming	Oq xusayni	22,0	16,0	55,3	46,8	15,4
		Pushti toyfi	6,0	8,5	61,5	57,5	6,5
2	Muqimov O'roz farming	Kitob surxaki	40,0	21,3	53,4	41,2	22,8
		Oq xusayni	30,0	15,5	69,5	61,3	11,8
		Qora kishmish	24,0	12,0	68,7	62,6	8,9
3	Qumsoy farming	Kitob surxaki	42,0	21,5	55,9	41,5	25,8
		Oq xusayni	30,0	15,5	68,3	57,3	16,1
		Qora kishmish	32,0	17,0	66,7	56,9	14,7
4	Suvli soy farming	Oq xusayni	28,0	16,0	71,2	60,6	14,9

In the flowering phase, the greatest lag in grapevine growth under the influence of anthracnose was observed in the "Kitob Surkhakhi" variety on vineyards belonging to the "Mukimov Uroz" and "Kumsoy" farms. In the "Mukimov Uroz" farm, the growth rate of sick plant shoots relative to healthy ones was 22.8%, while in the "Kumsoy" farm it was 25.8%.

On the vineyards of the "Sokhibkor" farm, the "Pushti Toyfi" variety lagged behind the growth of sick plant shoots compared to healthy ones, which amounted to 6.5%. Meanwhile, the length of healthy plant branches was 61.5

cm, while the length of infected plant branches was 57.5 cm. The prevalence of the disease in the "Kora kishmish" grape variety of the "Muqimov Uroz" farm was 24.0%, and as a result of its development in 12.0%, the growth rate of sympodial branches was 8.9% lower compared to healthy ones. In the vineyards of the "Muqimov Uroz" farm, where the "Qora kishmish" variety is grown, this figure reached 14.7%. This is due to the fact that the disease has developed in this vineyard up to 17.0%.

Conclusion: Thus, research has shown that the prevalence of anthracnose in vineyards and its strong development have a significant impact on the growth and development of sympodial branches.

As a result of our monitoring observations conducted on various grape varieties in the conditions of the Surkhandarya region, the growth lag of affected plant shoots compared to healthy ones was 6.5-25.8% in the flowering phase of the grape and 8.9-29.6% in the ripening phase of the grape fruits.

References:

1. Чертова, Т.С. Экологические проблемы защиты растений // Защита и карантин растений. - 1997. - №9. - С. 44.
2. Agrios G. N. Plant pathology. – Elsevier, 2005. Fifth ed. Elsevier Academic Press, Burlington, MA (2005). 922 pp.
3. Audenaert K., De Meyer G. B., Höfte M. M. Abscisic acid determines basal susceptibility of tomato to *Botrytis cinerea* and suppresses salicylic acid-dependent signaling mechanisms //Plant physiology. – 2002. – Т. 128. – №. 2. – С. 491-501.
4. Ahn, Soon Young, Seon Ae Kim, and Hae Keun Yun. "Glutathione S-transferase genes differently expressed by pathogen-infection in *Vitis flexuosa*." Plant breeding and biotechnology 4.1 (2016): – P.61-70.
5. Ammad F. et al. The potency of lemon (*Citrus limon* L.) essential oil to control some fungal diseases of grapevine wood //Comptes Rendus. Biologies. – 2018. – Т. 341. – №. 2. – С. 97-101.
6. Baroncelli, Riccardo, et al. "Characterization and epidemiology of *C. olletotrichum acutatum sensu lato* (*C. chrysanthemi*) causing *C. arthamus tinctorius* anthracnose." Plant Pathology 64.2 (2015): 375-384.
7. Barros, Luciane Bertoletti, et al. "Incidence of grape anthracnose on different *VITIS labrusca* and hybrid cultivars and rootstocks combination under humid subtropical climate." Australasian Plant Pathology 44 (2015): 397-403.
8. Barday S. et al. Morphological characterization and biological management of *Gloeosporium ampelophagum* (Pass.) Sacc causing anthracnose

of grapes in India //International Journal of Phytopathology. – 2022. – T. 11. –
№. 2. – C. 181-194.

